

Assessment of Land surface Temperature of Kolkata Urban Agglomeration, West Bengal, India

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Abstract

Kolkata Urban Agglomeration is one of the third largest urban agglomeration as well as third largest rapidly urbanizing, oldest and densely populated city in India. Due to urbanization and industrialization, the number of built-up areas are increasing and replacing the vegetation and land cover area. As urbanization is known as one of the most contributing factors for urban warming, so it is necessary to express the pattern of urban warming and degradation of land vegetation. Remote sensing and GIS with statistical procedure have enabled continuous monitoring land surface temperature (LST) and its correlation to land use and land cover change (LULCC). Landsat image creates an opportunity to study land surface temperature. This study to estimate LST through thermal bands (10 & 11) with Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) using Landsat 8 (OLI / TIRS) satellite data through ArcGIS software. Mean LST varied from 302.3°C to 276.5°C. A weakly positive correlation was observed between NDVI and LST ($R^2 = 0.0159$). It is found that the correlations between Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) depend on the time of season and day. The correlation between NDVI and LST for winter is positive, but summer is negative. The combined knowledge of LST and NDVI is necessary for understanding eco-environmental change and human-environmental interactions.

Keyword- Land Surface Temperature (LST), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Kolkata Urban Agglomeration (KUG), Remote Sensing, GIS

1. Introduction:

In 1947 AD Kolkata city is the capital of West Bengal state, and former national capital (1772 AD – 1911 AD) of British India. Actual rapid urbanization started to plague Kolkata from the 1650s. Within 1961 AD, its population exceeded 20,000 and it was declared a municipality in 1965 AD. After the period, people are being migrated to here, all part of India for various purposes and so to accompany them the building is built in an exponential rate. At present 2020 AD population reach about fifteen millions. Urbanization and industrialization has changed the existing natural of land surfaces with the modern land use (LU) i.e. buildings, roads and other construction, which indicates vegetation loss. Human population in the form of settlements and industrial area has a negative impact on the eco-environment as well as eco-environmental quality. Therefore, it is mandatory to have detailed information about spatiotemporal land use changes and their increasing rate. Land use should be matched with the land capability and at the same time, it should respect the eco-environment, and global climate systems (UNEP, 1996; Suraj et al., 2018).

Land surface temperature (LST) is fundamental parameter for understanding land surface characteristics, such as land use and land cover (LULC), vegetation type, and climate change. It can provide information about the surface, physical properties and climate which plays a role in many environmental processes (Dousset et al., 2003; Weng et al., 2004; Jiménez-Muñoz et al., 2014). LST used for an extensive variety of scientific studies (Running et al., 1994; Vining and Blad, 1992; Diak and Whipple, 1995; Crago et al., 1995; Kimmura and Shimizu, 1994). It can provide surface temperature of the ground and also information about the surface physical properties and climate play a role in numerous environmental processes (Sanjay K. Jain et al. 2007; Dousset & Gourmelon 2003; Weng, Lu & Schubring 2004). Landsat 8 comes with two different sets of images from Operation Land Imager (OLI) with nine bands (30 m resolution, except band 8 with 15 m resolution) and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS 1 & 2) with two bands (band 10 and band 11 with 100 m resolution) which is useful in providing more accurate surface temperatures.

Normalized difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is the one of the most widely utilized and significant remote sensing indicators which have been created to quantify ecological status (Hanqiu Xu, et al., 2019).

Higher NDVI maps the presence of vegetation on a pixel basis, which is the amount or condition of vegetation within a pixel. Lowest LSTs usually are found in high NDVI areas. This negative correlation between NDVI and LST is positive significant for urban climate and eco-environmental studies (Yuan and Bauer, 2007). Weng et al. (2004) found that the vegetation fraction has a slightly negative correlation with LST. But it's found that the correlations between LST and NDVI depend on the season-of-year and time-of-day. Correlation between NDVI and LST is found in winter and warm seasons are strong positive and strong negative, respectively. Nonetheless, Karnieli et al. (2006) establish that the northern ecosystems at high latitudes are characterized by positive correlations among LST and NDVI.

This paper considers only NDVI as a main cause of change in land surface temperature (LST). In this study, we investigate the effects of urban land use change on the land surface temperature in the Kolkata Urban Agglomeration based on the remote sensing analysis and zonal statistic methods. This paper focuses on the relation of NDVI with LST and pattern of temperature change and forecasts the climate change-related risks, supports on capacity building, policy and decision making of the agglomeration for certain NDVI.

2. Methods and materials

2.1 Study area

Kolkata Urban Agglomeration (KUA) also identified as Kolkata Metropolitan Area (KMA) which is the largest urban area in Eastern India and third largest urban agglomeration as well as third largest city in India (14.72 million) after the National Capital Region (46 million) and Mumbai Metropolitan Area (20.7 million), with population density of 7950 persons per Sq. Km. (2011 Census). The study area is situated between the latitudes of 22° 0'19" N to 23°0'1" N and the longitudes of 88°0'4" E to 88°0'33" E. It covers an area of over 1851.41 sq. km. and its elevation varies from 1.5 m to 9 m (5ft. to 30 ft.) from sea level (Fig. 1.0). This area has communicable linear urban prototype along both east and west bank of the river Hooghly, within the lower Ganges Delta, which is one of the lifelines of Southern Bengal. The agglomeration is surrounded by rural hinterland lying as a circle around the metropolitan area and acting as a shielding green belt (KMC, 2015). It consists of a complex set of administrative entities of 3 important municipal corporations (MC) i.e. Kolkata, Howrah and Chandernagore, 38 municipalities, 77 Census towns (CT), 16 outgrowths and 445 rural villages or Gram panchayat.

The annual mean temperature is around 24.8 °C; monthly mean temperatures ranges from 15 °C to 30 °C. Extreme temperature is observed over 40 °C (104 °F) during the month of May and June. Lowest temperature ranges from 9 °C – 11 °C during the months of December and January. While the highest and lowest recorded air temperature is 43.9 °C and 5 °C respectively. The average annual rainfall is 1,582 mm. The maximum rainfall occurs during the monsoon in August (306 mm). The study region receives 2,528 hours of sunshine per annum, with the maximum sunlight in March.

Fig. 1. The location map of Kolkata Urban Agglomeration

Land use analysis of Kolkata urban agglomeration has revealed a decline of vegetation from 33.6 % (1980) to 7.36 % (2010). The economic development of Kolkata urban agglomeration has been accompanied by a large influx of population and much of the farmland has given way to impervious built-up areas.

2.2 Methodology:

2.2.1 Data resources and pre-processing:

This study uses images from Landsat 8 OLI / TIRS on 2020-01-17 from United States Geological Survey (USGS, <http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>). The path/row was 138/44. Due to the focuses on the relation of greenness and heat. The authors used ArcGIS 10.8, ERDAS imagine 14, Microsoft Office 2010 and IBM SPSS statistics 26 software to complete radiometric correction of the remote sensing images, as well as to carry out this study. During the pre-processing of datasets, the gray value or digit number (DN) of the multispectral bands, converted into the reflectivity values of the sensor, used the Fast Line-of-sight Atmospheric.

2.2.2 Normalized Differential Vegetation Index (NDVI):

Vegetation is the most delicated factor to specify the quality of regional eco-environment. Greenness denoted Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) can reflect biomass, leaf area index, and vegetation coverage (Rouse *et al.*, 1973).. Furthermost researchers recommend that the NDVI is sensitive to low density vegetation, and it is particularly suitable for urban areas with high densities of built-up land (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Liu *et al.*, 2017). After conversion of the digital numbers (DN) to reflectance, the NDVI is expressed by the following equation (Rouse, J.W. *et al.*, 1973; Tucker *et al.*, 1979; Jeevalakshmi *et al.*, 2016; Giannini *et al.*, 2015; Hanqiu *et al.*, 2019):

$$NDVI = (\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}) / (\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red}) \tag{1}$$

Where, *NIR* and *Red* represent the DN values from the Near Infrared band 5 (0.85 – 0.88 μm) and Red band 4 (0.64 – 0.67μm) of Landsat 8 (OLI / TIRS) image, respectively. The NDVI value range between – 1.0 to +1.0, Negative values of NDVI may point to water bodies and snow cover, while greater than 0.5 values specified dense vegetation cover (Ozelkan, E. *et al.*, 2005; Mohammad Zare *et al.*, 2019).

2.2.3 Land Surface Temperature (LST):

Landsat data have used for LST study (Ding *et al.*, 2013; Erener *et al.*, 2012; Kaul *et al.*, 2012; Xiao *et al.*, 2007). The standard method for recovering LST from raw Landsat datasets requires the conversion of the DN values of the TIRS bands (Bands 10 and 11 in Landsat 8) into at-satellite spectral radiance values (L_λ) (Chander *et al.*, 2009; Xu *et al.*, 2009; USGS, 2016b; Mohammad Zare, *et al.*, 2019) and then into the at-satellite brightness temperature (BT), which is calculated beneath an assumption of unity emissivity (ε) and using pre-launch calibration constants (Chander *et al.*, 2009; Xu *et al.*, 2009; USGS, 2016b).

In order to preprocess the satellite images, the DN of TIRS and OLI bands were converted to spectral radiance and top of atmosphere (TOA) planetary reflectance. For conversion from a satellite temperature to land surface temperature as well as DN to radiance the following equation was used (USGS. *Landsat 8 Data users Handbook*, 2016):

$$L_{\lambda} = M_L * Q_{cat} + A_L \tag{2}$$

Where, L_λ is spectral radiation (Watts/ (m²*sr*μm)), M_L is Band specific multiplicative rescaling factor from the metadata, (RADIANCE_MULT_BAND_n), Where ‘n’ is the band number. (10 or 11 for Landsat 8), Q_{cat}= Level 1 value in DN or Corresponds to band 10 & 11, and A_L is Band specific additive rescaling factor from the metadata, (RADIANCE_ADD_BAND_n), Where ‘n’ is the band Number 10 or 11 (OLI/TIRS).

TIRS data were converted from spectral radiance to brightness temperature (BT_i):

$$BT_i = \{K_2 / \ln [(K_1/L_{\lambda}) + 1]\} - 273.15 \text{ (in } ^{\circ}C) \tag{3}$$

Where, BT_i is top of atmosphere (TOA) brightness temperature for TIRS band *i* (is 10 & 11 for TIRS) in Kelvin or Degree Celsius, K₁ = Band specific coefficients are thermal conversion constant from the metadata. (K1_CONSTANT_BAND_n), Where ‘n’ is the band Number 10 or 11 for Landsat -8 (Table 1), K₂ = Band specific thermal conversion constant from the metadata. (K2_CONSTANT_BAND_n), Where ‘n’ is the band Number (10 & 11 for Landsat 8).

In this process, the temperature results will be estimated in Celsius, the radiant temperature is adjusted by adding the absolute Zero which is approximately to – 273.15°C.

Table 1: The values of λ , Quantized calibration pixel and Spectral radiance for Landsat bands

Satellite	Band	λ (μm)	Thermal conversion constants (Parameter i)	
			K1	K2
Landsat – 8 (OLI/TIRS)	10	10.895	774.8853	1321.0789
	11	12.005	480.8883	1201.1442

Source: NASA (2013), USGA (2015)

The same to be implemented for the Band 11, from the equation we can get Band 10 radiance and Band 11 Radiance as an output.

Calculated to P_v from NDVI values obtained in formula 2. It gives the estimation of area under each land cover type. The vegetation and bare soil magnitudes are acquired from the NDVI of clean pixels (Zahir, 2020). Values of $NDVI_v$ and $NDVI_s$ is 0.5 and 0.2 respectively, were proposed to apply in global conditions while the value for vegetated surfaces ($NDVI_v = 0.5$) may be too low in some cases, for higher resolution data over cultivated sites, $NDVI_v$ can reach 0.8 – 0.9 (Wang, F., et al., 2015). Proportion of vegetation in mixed pixels to be estimated using the equation (Zahir, 2020):

$$P_v = \left(\frac{(NDVI - NDVI \text{ minimum})}{(NDVI \text{ maximum} - NDVI \text{ minimum})} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Where, P_v are the Proportion of Vegetation, NDVI is the DN values from NDVI Image, NDVI minimum and maximum value is minimum and maximum DN values from NDVI Image, respectively.

LST is largely dependent on the surface roughness, nature of vegetation cover etc. (JavedMallick et al., 2008). LST is the average emissivity (ϵ) of an element of the earth surface calculated from NDVI values. ϵ is calculated according to the empirical formula of Van de Griend and Owe (1993). NDVI is expressed as the equation:

$$\epsilon = 0.004 * P_v + 0.986 \quad (5)$$

When, $NDVI < 0$, ϵ is 1 (the emissivity of water body is close to 1).

When NDVI is 0 – 0.157, the vegetation coverage is very low, and ϵ is 0.92. When $NDVI > 0.727$ then ϵ is 1 (Qin et al., 2004).

The LST is the radiative temperature which calculated using TOA brightness temperature (BT), wavelength of emitted radiance, LST is calculated using equation (Orhan and Yakar, 2016):

$$LST = BT_i / [1 + (\lambda * BT / C_2) * \ln(\epsilon)] \quad (6)$$

Where, BT is TOA brightness temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), λ = Wavelength of emitted radiance (Table -2), $C_2 = h * c / s = 14387.685 \mu\text{m K}$; h = Planck's constant = $6.626 * 10^{-34} \text{Js}$; s = Boltzmann constant = $1.38 * 10^{-23} \text{J/k}$; c = Velocity of light = $2.998 * 10^8 \text{m/s}$.

3. Results and Discussion:

Figure 2 depicts the NDVI image generated by using Landsat 8 OLI data of the study area acquired on 17th January 2020. Here, the maximum and the minimum NDVI was 0.442 and -0.118, respectively, mean and standard deviation (SD) value of the study area is 0.137 and 0.076, respectively. Higher value of NDVI shows the more dense vegetation (forest) while lower value shows the water bodies. Paper template from study shows that the NDVI high at the periphery of the agglomeration and lowest at the heart of the urban agglomeration mainly 3 important municipal corporations (MC) i.e. Kolkata, Howrah and Chandernagore; 38 municipalities and 77 Census towns (CT) of the study area. Moderate NDVI range can be noticed on the translation zone of urban and village of Kolkata urban agglomeration.

The LST map for the agglomeration shows that the LST value range between 29.80°C to 15.79°C (Figure 3). Mean temperature is 22.41°C and 1.051 is the standard deviation (SD) in our research area. Altitude is the principal factor in the spatial variation of temperature (DHM, 2005). Paper template from study shows that the temperature decreases from the heart of the urban agglomeration to the periphery. Extreme temperature rages noticed in the heart of the urban area.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of NDVI over Kolkata Urban Agglomeration in 2020

The relationship between the LST and NDVI has widely documented in the literature (Chen, 2006; Weng, 2001 & 2006) Karl Pearson’s correlation coefficients have been computed between NDVI and LST over the study area using SPSS software. Figure 4b the scatterplot shows the correlation (pixel by pixel) between LST with NDVI for the study agglomeration. LST has a slight positive ($R^2 = 0.0159$) association with NDVI as well as vegetation cover. It means that wherever there is high NDVI, the surface temperature is high and vice versa. For winter seasons, the correlation between NDVI and LST is positive. The strong negative correlations between LST and NDVI are only found during the warm seasons (Kaufmann et al., 2003; Donglian et al., 2007).

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of Land Surface Temperature over the Kolkata Urban Agglomeration in 2020

Figure4: (a) Scattered plot between LST and NDVI; (b) Correlation analysis of NDVI and LST.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

The study shows that there is high rate of urban area enhancement due to high the population influx and unsuitable land use plan. As a result, productive cultivated land, vegetated area and open area are being interchanged by the concrete structures. This study area rapidly facing a rise in the temperature in summer and winter for different time intervals. Regarding the determination of the appropriate approach for LST prediction, we use NDVI. In this present study, it is found that the correlations between LST and vegetation depend on the season-of-year and time-of-day. For winter season, the correlation between NDVI and LST and correlation coefficient from NDVI to LST are positive. The cooling effect of vegetation on LST is much stronger during daytime than the nighttime. Further investigations will require for analyzing the more recent change in temperature and vegetation as well as more updated spatiotemporal data databases, and also will be require of long term spatial climate data for statistical analysis of better understanding the pattern of temperature and relation between NDVI and LST, climatic change and extreme eventuality.

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